

PB-WDS spectrometer for high energy resolution in-air PIXE measurements

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6598486

ABSTRACT

The new parallel-beam Wavelength dispersive (PB-WDS) x-ray spectrometer has been installed at the upgraded external beamline at the Microanalytical Centre of the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) in Ljubljana. The spectrometer combines polycapillary x-ray lens for efficient x-ray collection and diffraction on a flat crystal analyzer to reach high energy resolution. The spectrometer is designed for tender x-ray energy range (2-6 keV) so it is enclosed within a He bag to eliminate in-air x-ray absorption. Here we report the results of first characterization measurements yielding basic properties of the new setup. With this the commissioning phase has been completed and the spectrometer is now available for external users (Deliverable 21.7).

1. INTRODUCTION

At the Microanalytical Center of the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) in Ljubljana hosting a 2 MV Tandem accelerator, micro-PIXE analysis is regularly performed at the microprobe beamline based on the triplet quadrupole lens system from Oxford Microbeams (OM-150) [1] and applied successfully to biomedical applications [2-3]. While in these applications we are usually looking for maximal lateral resolution and the size of the scanning area is usually of the order of mm² and lower, we have recently upgraded our external beamline to extend the capabilities towards in-air PIXE imaging across relatively large sample surface area (~ 1 cm²) with lateral resolution of sub 100 μm [4].

In parallel with this upgrade we have also started to develop a novel parallel beam wavelength dispersive (PB-WDS) x-ray crystal spectrometer combining high-energy resolution ($\Delta E/E \sim 10^{-3}$) with large acceptance angle provided by X-ray polycapillary optics. The new setup is coupled to the upgraded external-beam providing focused proton beam and is used to perform PIXE measurements in ambient atmosphere with enhanced energy resolution and sensitivity. Here we are reporting the basic concept of this setup and provide its main characteristics.

2. SPECTROMETER DESIGN

Wavelength dispersive crystal spectrometers are predominantly aiming at high resolving power and they are typically large instruments requiring rather complicated alignment and operation procedures. Despite that curved crystals in various focusing geometries are used to enhance the overall efficiency, the solid angle of X-ray collection for these instruments is still rather small. The

PB-WDS spectrometer combines polycapillary X-ray optics and Bragg diffraction on the flat crystal. The use of X-ray half-lens provides large solid angle of X-ray collection, while the energy resolution is defined by the divergence of the X-rays exiting the polycapillary semi lens reaching typically few tenths of a degree. Such PB-WDS system is perfectly suited for the analysis using focused primary beam with fixed position and have so far been employed in microanalysis performed with electron microscopes [5] and for X-ray microfluorescence analysis [6]. When coupled to focused proton beam the PB-WDS setup can be used to perform also micro-PIXE analysis.

The basic working principle of the spectrometer is shown schematically in Fig. 1. The polycapillary X-ray semi-lens positioned at the focal distance relative to the sample plane is used to collect the

Figure 1: (top) A schematic picture of the PB-WDS setup. (bottom) A photo of the spectrometer within the He chamber installed at our external beam and a closer view of the beamline end with the polycapillary tip, beam exit nozzle and the tip of the Si(Li) detector.

emitted X-rays with large solid angle and convert a divergent X-ray fluorescence into a quasi-parallel x-ray beam, which is further directed toward a flat analyzer crystal rotated at the Bragg angle corresponding to particular wavelength. Diffracted x-rays are collected with an X-ray detector positioned symmetrically on the other side of the normal to the crystal surface. Since the X-ray beam exiting the polycapillary is almost parallel, the polycapillary-crystal and the crystal-detector distances are not really crucial for the overall design. Our spectrometer is designed for the tender X-ray range (2–6 keV). In order to remove large in-air x-ray absorption at these low x-ray energies the whole setup is enclosed within a He bag. The polycapillary lens is also filled with He and sealed with 12.7 μm Be window at both ends. This leaves us with just a 10 mm air gap corresponding to the focal distance of the lens which is small enough to provide efficient collection of x-rays down to 2 keV.

3. MAIN COMPONENTS

3.1 Polycapillary optics

The main component of the new PB-WDS setup is the polycapillary x-ray optics providing large solid angle of x-ray collection and the conversion of emitted fluorescence into parallel beam. We are using the polycapillary semi-lens manufactured by XOS (<http://www.xos.com/>). The main specifications of the polycapillary optics are given in Table 1. The parameters were optimized, taking into account the main properties of the focused proton beam at our new external beam in particular the beam size on the sample and the required tender X-ray fluorescence detection energy range. The polycapillary is mounted on the motorized linear micro stage MTS-65 manufactured by PImiCos (<http://www.pimicos.com>), which enable to adjust precisely the distance between the polycapillary optics and the target with respect to the focal distance of the lens. The full travel range of the stage is 13 mm with bi-directional repeatability around 5 μm .

Input focal distance	10 mm
Input collection angle	65 mSr
Output beam diameter	6 mm
Input field of view	$\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$
Transmission efficiency	15% at 1.5keV, 8% at 2keV, 11% at 3keV, 12% at 5keV, 5% @8keV
Output divergence	< 5 mrad
Enclosure length and diameter	33 mm; 10 mm; He filled with 12.7 μm Be window at both ends

Table 1: Polycapillary optics characteristics

3.2 Crystals and detector

The crystal is, together with the detector, mounted on the θ - 2θ goniometer. The goniometer is built from two separate PImiCos RS40 rotation stages providing bi-directional repeatability of $\pm 0.04^\circ$. The stages are assembled together and aligned to the same rotation axis with concentricity less than $\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$. Within given mechanical arrangement of the whole setup the Bragg angles of 35° – 80° can be reached. In order to cover the tender energy range, three different flat analyzer crystals are used. The list of currently available crystals is given in Table 2 together with the corresponding working energy range covered by a particular crystal within the first order of reflection. The size of the

crystals is 70 mm(width) times 30 mm (height). After diffraction by a flat crystal analyzer X-rays are detected with a 25 mm² Amptek XR-100CR: Si-PIN detector with 0.5 mil thick Beryllium window.

A dedicated home-made software was written in the LabVIEW programming environment to access the goniometer motor controllers and the detector read out. Within the acquisition procedure the scanned energy interval is defined, as well as the step size and the acquisition time for a single point. The final spectrum is recorded in a point-by-point scanning mode according to the corresponding Bragg angles calculated from the initially given energy input values.

crystal	2d [Å]	Energy range [keV]
Ge(111)	6.532	1.9 – 3.3
LiF(200)	4.027	3.1 – 5.4
LiF(220)	2.848	4.4 – 7.5

Table 2: List of available crystals with corresponding 2d lattice spacing and covered energy range.

4. FIRST EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The energy resolution of the PB-WDS spectrometer was determined from a series of K x-ray PIXE spectra recorded on a set of pure reference targets ranging from P to Fe in order to cover the full

Figure 2: K α PIXE spectra of P, K and Ti recorded with the PB-WDS spectrometer. P spectrum was recorded on a K₃PO₄ sample using the Ge(111) crystal. K spectrum was recorded from a homogenized pellet pressed from biological tissue sample (*Thlaspi praecox* Wulf.) containing appr. 20% of K, LiF(200) crystal analyzer was used in this measurement. Ti spectrum was recorded on a metallic target using LiF(220) crystal.

energy range. 3 MeV proton beam was used in these measurements, the beam was focused to appr. $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$. As an example, $K\alpha$ x-ray emission spectra of P, K and Ti recorded with Ge(111), LiF(200) and LiF(220) crystals, respectively, are presented in Figure 2. The acquisition time for a single point was 6 seconds in case of P and Ti measurements and was increased to 10 seconds for K spectrum due to lower content of potassium in the sample.

The final experimental energy resolution values were determined by fitting each measured $K\alpha$ spectrum with the model spectrum composed of two Voigt functions. The natural Lorentzian width was constrained to match the natural K, L atomic level widths tabulated in [7], and the width of the Gaussian component describing the spectrometer response function was a free fitting parameter. An additional Voigt profile was added on the high energy side of the $K\alpha$ line to account for the $K\alpha L^1$ multiple ionization satellite line. An example of such fit is presented in Fig 3. for the Ti spectrum, and the finally extracted energy resolution values are tabulated in Table 3. Tabulated values correspond to the FWHM of the Gaussian component of the Voigt profile.

Figure 3: Ti $K\alpha$ PIXE spectrum recorded with the PB-WDS spectrometer. A model spectrum described in the text is fitted to the experimental one in order to determine the energy resolution of the spectrometer.

crystal		E (keV)	ΔE (eV)
Ge(111)	P	2.014	3.45 ± 0.03
	S	2.308	6.55 ± 0.04
	Cl	2.622	12.81 ± 0.32
LiF(200)	K	3.314	6.56 ± 0.03
	Ca	3.692	10.96 ± 0.11
LiF(220)	Ti	4.511	6.91 ± 0.09
	Cr	5.415	15.99 ± 0.20
	Fe	6.404	18.52 ± 0.54

Table 3: Experimentally determined absolute energy resolution values determined from $K\alpha$ spectra measured on a set of reference targets.

Finally, the analytical potential of the new PB-WDS setup is demonstrated by the spectrum recorded on the representative biological sample. The analyzed material was the Cd/Zn metal hyperaccumulating plant *Thlaspi praecox*. In case of standard PIXE analysis based on spectra recorded by the EDS detector the detection of cadmium L lines is obscured by the presence of strong potassium $K\alpha$ line, which is one of the major elements presented in the plant tissue. Because of this energy overlap the Cd K lines are usually used in PIXE analysis yielding relatively low count rates and consequently poor sensitivity due to low Cd σ_K cross section. With the PB-WDS spectrometer providing high energy resolution the Cd $L\alpha$ line is well resolved from the neighboring potassium $K\alpha$ signal and with this increasing significantly the sensitivity for Cd detection. Despite relatively low concentration of Cd in the sample around 1400 ppm as verified by several different X-ray fluorescence techniques [8], the $L\alpha$ line of Cd in *Thlaspi praecox* sample is recorded without any major problem as presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: The measured PIXE spectrum of *Thlaspi praecox* hyperaccumulating plant recorded with the PB-WDS spectrometer. LiF(200) crystal analyzer was used in this measurement, the acquisition time was 10 sec/point.

5. CONCLUSION

A new PB-WDS x-ray spectrometer has been installed at the upgraded external beamline at the Microanalytical Centre of the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) in Ljubljana. The spectrometer is designed for tender X-ray range (2-6 keV) and is therefore enclosed in a He bag. It provides PIXE measurements with high energy resolution $\Delta E/E \sim 2-4 \times 10^{-3}$ combined with a relatively high collection angle provided by the polycapillary x-ray optics. The spectrometer will be used to remove interferences between neighboring emission lines and enhance the sensitivity of PIXE analysis in case of trace elements with emission lines in the tender x-ray range. It will be used in parallel with the standard Si(Li) detector for in air PIXE imaging performed at our external beam.

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